

eScience Center Fellowship Programme 2022: Application Form

January 2022

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

1a. Details of the fellowship applicant

Surname, first name, title(s)	Gawehns, Daniela
Email address	gawehnsd@liacs.leidenuniv.nl
Institute	LIACS - Leiden Institute of Advanced Computer Science
Department	
Section	Data Science Research Program - EDA research group
Address	Niels Bohr Weg 1
Postcode	2333 CA Leiden
City	Leiden
Tel	

1b. What is your current occupation / career stage?

PhD candidate

Postdoctoral researcher

Assistant professor

Associate professor

Professor

Data steward

Research software engineer

Other, namely:

2a. Title of your proposed fellowship project

What is computational reproducibility - and how do we measure it?

2b. Summary for the eScience Center website (max 150 words)

More and more researchers provide analysis code and data along with their research papers. This is a laudable progress and enhances the transparency of research. Very little of this provided material is checked on its reproducibility, so if the results of the papers can be derived from the provided code and data. In this project, I am exploring what the minimum requirements for computational reproducibility are in the computational sciences. The product at the end of the project is a measurement tool to assess the computational reproducibility of research work in a fair and user-friendly manner.

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netherlands
eScience center**2c. In which of the four categories below does your project fit most closely?**

Please rank the four disciplines in order of relevance to your project (1: most closely related to your project, 4: least related to your project). This will be used to partner you with the most relevant point of contact at the eScience Center.

Discipline	Rank
Environment and sustainability	3
Natural sciences and engineering	1
Life sciences	2
Social sciences and humanities	4

FELLOWSHIP PROJECT PLAN

3. Project plan

Code, computational experiments or benchmarking are the basis for empirical research work within the computer sciences. Simulated data are often produced to show the efficacy and efficiency of a new method or algorithm and almost all claims need to be implemented in some form. Research software is hence at the core of computer science research.

This doesn't mean that the produced research software is tested or re-run outside of the individual researcher's computer. Very often, co-authors trust their colleagues to have produced the right implementation and will not re-run their code before submitting material to a conference or journal. While some conferences started to require code and data to be publicly shared along with the submitted article, most venues do not require this. Peer review is hence limited to the reasoning, argumentation, novelty and impact of the research paper. The assurance that code and data will lead to the presented results is left to those who want to build on the author's work and to enthusiastic reviewers.

In this project, I would like to explore how reproducibility of research results can be defined within the computational sciences and how a measure for the reproducibility of a research result might look like.

In a first step, I want to find out how my peers define computational reproducibility. For some subfields, pseudocode already satisfies the requirement while other fields will require to re-run an analysis from scratch. There are open questions such as: How do we deal with simulation studies? Is the code behind the simulations basis for the evaluation of the reproducibility or the simulated data? What do we do within the machine learning literature: do we require re-training of large models just to see if the code runs? Which intermediate results will help other researchers to reproduce research results and how many should we make available to satisfy a reproducibility criterion?

The first step will consist of a series of interviews, maybe extended by focus-group-type sessions on the raised criteria and topics. I envision to write short blog posts or summaries of the interviews (if the interviewees agree to be cited) to accompany the process.

In a second step, a questionnaire-type tool will be developed to assess the computational reproducibility of research within the computer sciences. To this end, topics and criteria raised during the interview stage of the project will guide the discussion during a workshop or a series of workshop-type sessions. During those workshops or meetings, participants will be invited to think along on the usability of an assessment tool, the wording of the different questionnaire items and how a final reproducibility score should be calculated. The final product will be presented in form of a joint research paper or technical report. The contacts made during the interview stage of this project will help with finding the right venue for the workshop.

The suggested project is not the first project or initiative looking into computational reproducibility, nor is it the first one focusing on the reproducibility of results in the computational sciences. Firstly, [The Turing Way](#) handbook is a great starting point for reproducible data science. I know members of the

community, which will hopefully help me find interesting interview partners beyond my own work environment. Secondly, Code-Check, an initiative by Daniel Nüst and Stephen Eglén, focuses on including reproducibility checks into the publishing pipeline. As a core member of Reprohack, we are already in touch with both researchers and I am sure they will be able to guide me, too. Lastly, I would like to mention two efforts by the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), leading to a series of community calls and a badging system for artifacts. An emerging interest group of the ACM held five community calls in 2021 to discuss the state of reproducibility of computational research and summarized their findings in several blog posts. Another effort are so called artifact badges that several special interest groups of the ACM are already offering to their members. Until recently, I have not had contact with the researchers behind these efforts. I will reach out to them during the interview phase.

Ideally, this project will lead to a questionnaire-type tool to rate the reproducibility of research material during peer review in a user-friendly and standardized manner. This would increase the transparency and quality of research software within the publishing process.

I am a fourth year PhD student within an institute that covers many different types of computational sciences. This will give me access to different points of views for the first part of the project plan, namely finding an initial set of interview partners. For the questionnaire, I will use the reproducibility feedback form by Reprohack as a first basis. Reprohack is an initiative that I have been involved in since 2019. During a Reprohack event, participants re-run analyses from donated research material and give authors extensive feedback on the reproducibility of their research. This feedback form will be a first basis for discussion and further development during the second phase of the project. Given my long involvement with the Reprohack community, I am aware of how different fields of research are approaching the topic of reproducibility, code and data sharing. Lastly, I have been organizing and facilitating different types of workshops online and offline for the last years. This includes workgroups for students, reprohacks, train-the-trainer workshops and interactive sessions on responsible research. I am a certified Carpentries trainer and a trainer for VIRTUE-trainings in research integrity and ethics.

4. Fellowship timeline

As I will be on maternity leave from June 2022 to Oktober 2022, I took the liberty to move the timeline to stretch from Oktober 2022 to Oktober 2023. I hope this can be facilitated in case the fellowship is granted.

First Phase: Interviews

October 2022 - March 2023

Second Phase: Workshops

April 2023 - August 2023

Third Phase: Wrap-up and Write-up

September 2023- Oktober 2023

5. Fellowship budget specification

Please paste a budget that specifies how your personal fellowship budget will be used below. Choose between:

Personal Budget of 3000 Euro

For the second part of the project, a series of workshops or workshop-type events are planned. Ideally, those would be in-person workshops, even though remote ones are more accessible and make it easier to gather an international crowd. The personal budget will be used to host one in-person workshop in the Netherlands or to organize a conference workshop in Europe. In the first case, the main cost will be rent of a venue and catering, in the second case, I would spend the money on the conference fee and travel cost for myself. If a remote workshop seems more feasible and useful to the project, I will use the money to pay for online infrastructure and shipping of workshop kits. A more detailed budget is not yet possible at the moment as I would like to gather input from the interviewees on where and how to best gather participants from the (very broad) CS community.

36 hrs of in-kind expertise

The e-science center expertise will be used to organize the workshop or workshop series. If there are hours left-over, those might be used to build a website to share the results of this project in a nice manner.

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

6. Statements by the applicant

The eScience Center strictly applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU (see www.eugdpr.org). In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants must strictly apply these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

Applicants are asked to endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

- I endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG), as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- I endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP. **If 'NO', then please justify, and contact the eScience Center before submitting the application.**
- I have completed this form truthfully.

Name: Daniela Gawehns

Place: Leiden

Date: April 8th, 2022

To submit your application, send the completed form to fellowship@esciencecenter.nl. The deadline for application is April 11, 2022, 14:00 CET.

Turn to the next page for an optional section.

OTHER INFORMATION (OPTIONAL)**7. A little more about you**

The following section is **optional and will not affect your application**. Only share this information if you wish to share it. At the eScience Center, we are interested in the backgrounds of our project partners and future fellows. Therefore, we have a few questions about you.

7a. Which of the following disciplines are relevant to the research / work you do on a daily basis?

Agricultural or Environmental Sciences
Biomedical or **Health Sciences**
Chemistry
Civil, Mechanical, Chemical, or Nuclear Engineering
Computer Science or Electrical Engineering
Earth Sciences
Economics or **Business**
Genetics, Genomics, or **Bioinformatics**
High Performance Computing
Humanities
Library and Information Sciences
Life Sciences
Mathematics or Statistics
Medicine
Organismal **Biology**
Physical Sciences
Planetary Sciences
Psychology or Neuroscience
Social Sciences
Space Sciences
Research Support

7b. What gender do you identify as?

Female
Male
Non-binary
Prefer not to say

7c. In which country did you complete the majority of your education?

Netherlands

7d. What is your nationality?

German

7e. Your GitHub, Twitter, and / or LinkedIn accounts:

github: DanielaGawehns, twitter: @dgawehns

